

Hain: Oman Tourism Mobile App

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Abstract:

It is widely known that there are numerous technological devices available in the world that people use and that they have become a part of our daily lives. This is no different in the Sultanate of Oman. There are many smartphone applications that have been developed by Omanis to serve the people of Oman. "Tm Done!" is one example. A country such as Oman is very fortunate to possess a deep cultural heritage as well as numerous natural and cultural resources. Oman's tourism sector is one of the largest contributors to its economy and plays a major role in it. In this sense, it is extremely critical to support the tourism sector and enhance the technology that pertains to this sector. For the purpose of supporting this sector and to make it easier for residents and tourists in Oman to access information about events, we proposed to develop a new mobile application that would enable them to access information easily.

Our proposal in this project is to develop a mobile application titled Hain. With the Hain platform, it is possible to display events in Oman, such as conferences, concerts, and exhibitions, by detecting their location on a map and finding the current and upcoming events. Hain, the chosen name of our application, is commonly used by Omani residents as a slang term for "Where". The proposed application will provide companies and organizations with the ability to post their events, such as conferences, exhibitions, and annual celebrations. Through the application, users will be able to view a map interface that displays the information that these organizations and companies have uploaded regarding their locations, dates, and other details of the events. In most venues used to hold events, visitors have trouble navigating their way inside the buildings. The solution to this problem is coming in the form of the Hain. This feature provided by this application in the form of blueprints of the buildings that are used to host the events. This will allow users to find their way around the building easily.

One of the features that make this mobile application unique is the fact that tourists are able to join in the conversation on the App and through the use of opinion mining, they will be able to find the information that they are looking for. Opinion mining is defined as the process of using natural language processing, text analysis and computational linguistics to identify and categorize the opinions expressed, whether they are negative or positive. In this project an opinion mining technique for tourism in Oman is presented that will enable tourists to find the events in Oman that has positive comments and to be able to give their opinion about their experience of attending the events.

We have decided to develop our project using a piece of software called "App inventor", which we intend to use in order to execute our plan. It was decided that we did not want to design a website for tourism in Oman since there are already a lot of pages available for that purpose. It is

also predictable that users like to use their smartphones while travelling, therefore, a mobile app will be more convenient for them. As a final note, this mobile application will be very helpful to the authorities, such as the Ministry of Tourism, in promoting tourism in Oman.